

SCIENTIFIC APPROACHES TO INNOVATIVE THINKING

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Abstract. *In the article the study of the scientific, socio-philosophical foundations and epistemological foundations of innovative thinking shows that the human consciousness, interest, desire to know, to improve the environment differs from other beings with its innovative features, human inclination and ability to innovative research, dynamism, progressiveness to social life. features are displayed.*

Keywords: *innovative, conceptual, creative, thinking, philosophical, scientific, social, modernization, system, feature, factor.*

НАУЧНЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ИННОВАЦИОННОМУ МЫШЛЕНИЮ

Аннотация. *В статье исследование научных, социально-философских основ и гносеологических основ инновационного мышления показывает, что человеческое сознание, интерес, стремление к познанию, улучшению окружающей среды отличается от других существ своими инновационными особенностями, человеческими склонностями и способностями. инновационным исследованиям, динамизму, прогрессивности общественной жизни. отображаются функции.*

Ключевые слова: *инновационное, концептуальное, творческое, мышление, философское, научное, социальное, модернизация, система, особенность, фактор.*

The strategy of innovative development has been developed in the Republic of Uzbekistan, its conceptual issues, duties set given Although this process started with the independence of our Republic, in the next five years it became a social and national reality, the brand and international image of "New Uzbekistan" was formed. The third renaissance is the product of conceptual ideas, creative research and activity aimed at the innovative development of the country, as well as the "Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" (April 20, 2017), which was developed and adopted at the initiative of our President Sh.M. Mirziyoev, appearing as an expression. The core of innovative thinking is a philosophical outlook, in the words of INLapshin, "philosophical invention". Philosophical invention expresses the hunger for innovation in the human mind, the desire for new thoughts and approaches. It consists of a philosophical idea, a philosophical thought, an observation and a view of conceptual importance. Philosophy itself is a constant novelty, innovation. If we interpret innovation as a new idea, philosophy is exactly this idea. Philosophy, with its scientific methodological and fundamental importance, brings innovation to thinking, encourages thinking to new observations and conclusions. Even scientific and technical innovations with a more empirical aspect rely on philosophical inventions and look for their basis in them. Functional systems and social classification features of innovative thinking arise from its above scientific and social philosophical essence. Striving for innovation, modernization of social existence, production processes determines these functional systems and social classification features, gives them a

direction. In this way, striving for innovation, modernization is manifested in the form of deterministic factors that shape innovative thinking. The study and analysis of scientific approaches and definitions of innovative thinking show that it has the following functional systems, social and classification features:

- that is, innovative thinking comes as a type of scientific activity aimed at bringing innovation and discovery into social life, science;
- represents a worldview prone to innovation, development and change;
- acts as a creative, psychological institution that directs the rational searches and activities of a person to specific social goals;
- combined with social consciousness and social thought, reflects a new conceptual idea of a certain environment, society, group;
- has a social deterministic character;
- affects social existence, community life in the form of new spiritual reality, ideas, values;
- all conscious, rational activities of a person can be considered as the products of the influence of innovative thinking¹. This systematic, classification approach helps to reveal the scientific, socio-philosophical essence of innovative thinking. However, it is necessary to remember that not all products of thinking are innovative, sometimes thinking can be conservative and unscientific. Therefore, when we apply the above directions of thinking to innovative thinking, we refer to aspects of thinking that are prone to new research, scientific, technical and technological innovations. We explore not all forms and products of thinking, but those aspects that are prone to renewal and support a new approach, in the way of innovative thinking.

Functional systems of innovative thinking mean social spheres and institutions where innovation and new technologies are introduced, the changes observed in them, the social significance of these changes, and their tasks. Such functional systems are determined by the internal functions and characteristics of social spheres. For example, there are certain differences between the functions of innovation in the field of culture and the functions in the field of politics, economics or medicine. Innovation in the field of culture is focused on preservation and increase of material and spiritual wealth, introduction of international, new experiences in this regard.

Innovation in the field of politics is a type of activity aimed at effective management of society and state life. Innovation in the field of economy implies the production of goods and services, the organization of this process based on modern technology. Functional systems of innovative thinking require a good knowledge of the features and functions of the social sphere in which innovation is introduced. Knowing the problems in these areas and striving to solve them is the initial stage of innovation, but at the basis of innovation lies the goal of seriously affecting the industry, turning the innovation into a priority reality. Ignorance of this requirement turns innovative research into a palliative phenomenon, as a result of which the innovation does not produce significant results. The activities of the world's largest corporations and firms confirm that innovation can bring fundamental changes to the industry. For example, large corporations such as Apple, Microsoft, Macdonald can be an example¹.

Innovative thinking is a type of scientific activity, primarily related to science, aimed at bringing innovation to social life. Science is essentially a phenomenon that encourages the search

for new things, the organization of social life in accordance with new things, and the constant search for new things. Scientific research has never stopped, even in the times of inquisition, bigotry and totalitarianism, the human mind did not rest, it continued to strive to find new things.

However, in thinking about certain stages of social development (for example, the 9th-14th centuries called the "Eastern Renaissance", the 16th-17th centuries called the New Age, the Renaissance and Enlightenment periods), in the words of the famous historian L.N. Gumilev, "passionateness" (that is, revitalization, intensification, tension) is observed. Sociologists recognize these periods as separate stages of development of thought, culture and society. Today, the New Era (XVI-XVII centuries) is recognized as a special stage of scientific and technological development. From this period, man began to pay great attention to intellectual research, scientific and technical discoveries. In particular, the discovery of the steam locomotive, sewing machine and new technical tools made it possible to ease and increase the productivity of heavy manual labor, and to reach even the longest distances quickly and easily. Every scientific innovation was a product and achievement of human thinking, and ultimately, the development of society and civilization was evaluated according to scientific innovations. Today, it has become a common approach to evaluate and measure the progress achieved by mankind with scientific and technical discoveries. Humanity, human society has a dynamic nature, precisely because of these characteristics, they constantly strive for innovation, support new research. Development means the search for new things, the product of scientific discoveries.

Experts say that "humanity has been constantly searching to make its life comfortable and prosperous during the past period since its appearance on earth. The discovery of fire brought great convenience to the lives of primitive people. Their food is delicious, and the bitter cold is a little less. The discovery of fire in turn led to the discovery of metal. This created greater opportunities for people. Work and hunting tools made of metal were preferable and more convenient than stone tools. This led to great positive changes in agriculture and hunting. The invention of the wheel made great changes in human life. Now people had the opportunity to travel long distances and bring various goods from far away. There is another discovery made by mankind, which is no less important than the above-mentioned discoveries. The name of this is also quite mild, the intercontinental trade caravan route is the Great Silk Road. In history, the researcher is interested in the "jade road" that connected northern China with Khotan and Yarkent, the "dull (lazurite) road" that connected Iran, Mesopotamia, Syria, Egypt and Anatolia, the Urals, the Golden O It reveals that there was a "Northern Road" connecting Russia, Europe and Central Asia, scientific discoveries and researches were made in this geographical area. He writes, for example, "Due to Khorezm's trade relations with Middle Eastern countries, a wonderful type of pottery called "lustra" entered the region. "Several dozens of pieces and whole copies of Lustra pottery are known from Daryalik Lake Basin, Qavat Castle, Qizil Castle, Mizdahkhan, Shemahakal'ala and other monuments of the Khorezmshah era"². Therefore, the Great Silk Road and other trade centers cannot be considered separately from scientific and creative processes, each integrated relationship relies on some innovation and brings innovations. Since the genesis of thinking goes back to the first imaginations, trade and integration relations in the primitive period, it is necessary to consider rationalism in the New Age, belief in the power of intelligence, and science as a new stage of thinking. As Academician A.F. Losev wrote, from the mythology of the primitive period,

one can find a source and basis for any thought, new research³. Although thought continues to rely on this tradition, it is not completely dependent on it, and in many cases even openly opposes it.

In this place, it is possible to remember the philosophical heritage of B. Spinoza, Acosta, Feuerbach, Mansur Halloj, fundamental changes in social consciousness during scientific and technical revolutions. These changes were innovative.

Innovative thinking is a worldview prone to innovation, progress and change. The word "innovation" is derived from the Latin "in" and "novation" means new. So "innovation" means bringing in. According to its socio-philosophical essence, it is "a cultural reality, change, innovation, a new method, means, mechanisms used in the process of activity that was not present in the previous development of the object." At its center is a certain idea, worldview. Therefore, innovative thinking is a certain idea, a worldview aimed at introducing new things.

There is no person who does not have a certain worldview, but to have a worldview of innovative importance, awareness of scientific research is required. It is important not just a worldview, but a worldview built on the results of scientific research and inventions. But a person who is familiar with the laws of human thought, psychology and epistemological research knows that scientific research is not always new or innovative. Sometimes a researcher, scientist, engineer discoverer may not create something new after searching for a lifetime, and it is usual for some researches to repeat old scientific results, not much different from them. Scientific innovation is not required from studies aimed at generalization and study of empirical experiences, the study and generalization of empirical experiences itself is innovation. So, although the worldview and idea express a certain life approach, the epistemological interest of a person, it is not always an innovation, it can remain at the level of personal interest and need, and become narrow, sensitive experiences. In most cases, this is the case, so scientific discoveries are understood as a unique process, a reality.

We should mention one more aspect that no matter how the world view and idea affect human actions and activities, they often remain an internal, hidden, subjective phenomenon. It is both easy and difficult to find innovation from them. The easy part is that a subjective phenomenon can be interpreted in different ways, in the words of the ancient philosophers, "it is no easier to find black or a stain in something that appears white." For this, it is enough for the subject to focus his gaze on the second point of the white object. The hard part is that "every thesis has an antithesis." Worldview, idea is built on theses, expressed in theses. Thinking, consciousness can accept and evaluate these theses in different ways. That is why the innovation that comes in the form of a worldview, an idea may seem like a novelty today, and tomorrow it may be evaluated in the absolute opposite way. In science, there are discoveries that are considered absolutely new.

For example, the heliocentric theory of Galileo and Copernicus, the theory of relativity of A. Einstein, the periodic system of D. Mendeleev are among them. However, these doctrines and systems are not completely immutable, in recent years, quantum theory and geological research have made certain additions to them. These changes are not only related to the limitation of human thinking, but are also related to the wide, complex and changing nature of the objects and events that people are looking for¹.

A change of worldview and idea is not yet an innovation. For example, in the following years, the exchange and transformation of the scientific worldview with the religious worldview

is observed. Certain changes took place in the inner, spiritual life of people, theological knowledge and views about the transcendent were formed. But for some reason, we scientists do not call them innovation. This shows the difficulty of correctly assessing the transformation occurring in worldviews and ideas, the complexity of finding innovation in them. In the fields of management, economy, information communication, technology, it is manifested in concrete mechanisms, forms and methods, which are not difficult to develop and evaluate. Innovative thinking acts as a creative, psychological institution that directs the rational searches and activities of a person to specific social goals. In this place, four categories that require each other are noticeable: rational search and activity, social goals, creativity and psychological establishment.

Rational search and activity is a behavior based on human intelligence and expressing objective needs. A rational approach is the main sign of innovative thinking. Therefore, seeking novelty from irrational behavior is not common. The connection of rational research with objective needs gives vitality and relevance to scientific, philosophical and intellectual inventions. Rational research, which is based on objective, social goals, expresses them, even if they do not lead to any innovations and inventions, they advance human thinking and enrich it with something. In the process of this development, a psychological institution regarding the search for truth is formed in the mind. Therefore, it is not necessary to expect innovation and invention from all researches, but they should add something to human thinking. A psychological institution called to search for the true truth encourages the philosopher to create a stable ideal, to search for it, to protect it in any situation. Without this framework, the researcher will not have a clear idea of what he is looking for, and will follow any idea, concept or invention. Consistency in the search for truth is due to this principle.

Philosophical, intellectual invention, research, creativity, creative activity. Rationalizing this activity and directing it to objective needs has always raised various questions in philosophy.

With this in mind, IILapshin writes: "Any invention is an improvement, but it embodies the sign of consistency, sequence and creativity, because consistency synthesizes researches of qualitatively different order in the previous process"¹.

The American philosopher S. Langer called any shift in philosophy a novelty, a "new key" and based its symbolic nature on the connection with creativity and creative processes¹. At the same time, philosophers also mention the problem of connecting creative activity with social purpose. The individual psychological nature of creativity, even the leadership of a psychological institution in it, can only be effective through social purpose. The well-known psychologist N.Uznadze emphasizes that "psychological institution" as a reality close to the socio-spiritual ideal, has not only an individual sensitivity, but also a socio-practical, purposeful nature². The individual sensitive, reflexive nature of creativity and creative processes cannot remain only at the level of the individual, because the individual, the creator himself is a product of a certain social environment and ethnocultural stereotypes in it. This social environment and ethnocultural stereotypes sometimes have an open, transparent, sometimes closed, covert effect, but always undergo a synthesis of personal reflection, life experience, and the influence of the creative institution. Therefore, creative philosophy and psychology pay attention not only to individual interests, reflexive experiences, but also to their connection with social goals. Innovative thinking combined with social consciousness and social thinking expresses a certain conceptual idea. Even

simple scientific and technical innovations that do not express any idea are built on conceptual views. For example, the new tools created by the USA and Europe bring technicism and pragmatism into our lives with their external aesthetics, efficiency, ease of hard work, and expansion of opportunities. Burger, Red House, McDonald's, KFC do not just whet our appetite, they inculcate the Western lifestyle, the epicurean idea of "eat, drink, enjoy" into our social consciousness. Eating on the street is not a tradition in the Uzbek people, it is even condemned.

We took the above innovations as innovations, and now they are becoming popular.

Conceptual ideas in innovations are economic (identification of production processes and tools, creation of new products, increase of cultural services), political (introduction of new technologies, institutions, laws to the management of state and community life; expansion of opportunities to use modernization and democratic management mechanisms), legal (implementation of international legal norms, creation of legal norms aimed at ensuring freedom of speech and opinion), cultural-axiological (transforming new work methods, new ways of thinking into socio-cultural values), scientific-technical (scientific-technical formation of thinking, establishment of new personnel and institutions in this regard, joining global scientific and technical development), international integration (participation in solving regional and international problems, formation of the labor migration system, contributing to the establishment of a policy of peace and cooperation on earth) can be researched in such directions. Social, classification characteristics of innovative thinking also depend on these directions. For example, the social and classification characteristics of innovative innovations and updates introduced into the economic sphere include the production of new goods, the introduction of new technology, the expansion of management and marketing opportunities, the creation of national brand products through their use, a positive opinion about the activities of corporations, enterprises, and firms with the help of media centers. can be expressed in such ways as creating a charming image. It should be remembered that national goods, services and media centers form an innovative brand and international image. It is known from the experience of developed countries that no matter how important innovation is, it is equally important to create a brand, a charming image, and an international image. Companies that care about their image, brand, do not ignore any news related to the activities of the media centers.

They form and promote their brand, international image through mass media, media centers.

Innovative thinking has a socially deterministic character. Every new thing created and brought into life affects social thought, people's imaginations and encourages them to search for new things. It is due to the influence of this determinism that the social consciousness is mobilized, and people are interested in innovative ideas and developments in their hearts and minds.

According to the Russian philosopher NOLossky, "all human behavior has a deterministic nature, it is influenced by the human body or character, generation or social environment. Human will and creative search are also influenced by determinism"¹. From this point of view, innovation, as a creative search, is a reality that is born from the "social environment" and turns into social wealth, and as an intellectual property, it arouses interest in intellectual research and scientific innovation in people. Even scientific and technical innovations do not stay within the framework of one enterprise or corporation, they form the opinion of consumers through the goods and

products they make, intensify the competition in production, "who won". As a result, the consumer wins, that is, the innovative product, the product becomes a brand, social values. As T. Parsons said, "The goal of the economy is not to maximize production for the individual, but to maximize it in relation to the social value system"² That is, the innovation introduced to production and the economy is not maximized only for the needs of the individual consumer, but the social value system is maximized through And social values in the form of realities with a constant deterministic nature shape the life of society, manages "institutional systems" (T. Parsons), directs them to social goals.

Determinism and indeterminism meant by NOLossky can be seen in innovation when it expresses aspects related to antinomic phenomena such as effect and reflection, newness and oldness, creation and commandment. Innovation should not be understood as absolute newness, in any information or method something related to the past, oldness can be found. For example, flying to alien planets or "spaceships" are what we call scientific and technical innovation. But the genesis of these innovations can be interpreted as a product of fantastic ideas (flying carpets) in folk tales, which are ancient myths. "Flying carpets" are the first conceptual models of these interplanetary rockets, "saucers". Any innovation acquires an innovative character over time, its indeterministic aspect makes thinking and research consistent and systematic. The laws of dialectical development of social life made innovation and anovation, determinism and indeterminism a natural phenomenon. Therefore, innovation and anovation should be interpreted as the quality of natural aspects of social life. The tendency of thinking to newness is the basis of innovative research. Innovation is not just a desire, sensitive research emphasizes personal desires and interests, but it cannot be forgotten that it also requires concrete, practical actions. News needs to become a real relationship, to be objectified. The most common form of this is scientific and technical discoveries, so the term innovation often refers to such discoveries and inventions. There is a certain time and distance between the inclination of thinking to newness and its objectification.

The scientific and technical development of society depends on making this time and distance as short as possible. It does not have developed standards, but every society that strives for development, if we proceed from the requirements of today's scientific and technical development, first of all creates and supports socio-economic factors and effective mechanisms for introducing innovation into practice.

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